

Efficient and flexible Adaptive Particle Refinement for free-surface flows based on the RHOD-SPH scheme

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Abstract

In the SPH literature, the existing Adaptive Particle Refinement (APR) or similar multi-resolution techniques can be categorized into three main approaches, essentially driven by the discrete differential operators selected. When a conservative formulation is retained, either variable smoothing-length techniques or buffer regions are generally employed. By contrast, in formulations using accurate but non-conservative SPH operators, large variations of the particle size are achievable without requesting any specific treatment. However, because of the difficulties of such formulations in addressing the free surface, they have so far been restricted to internal flows. Recently, a Regularized High-Order Diffusive (RHOD)-SPH approach has been derived, in the context of single resolution. In this approach an accurate formulation is used inside the bulk of the fluid whereas a conservative one is preferred in the free-surface region. In the present work, we generalize this approach to APR, enabling large variations in particle size even in presence of a free-surface. To this end, an extension of the ingredients required in the RHOD-SPH approach is derived. Specifically, the Riemann-based diffusive terms and Particle Shifting Technique are generalized to the APR context. A particle splitting procedure is employed to enlarge the range of applications of the approach. The formulation is validated on five different 2D test cases, with a comparison with both single-resolution and reference results.

Keywords: Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics; Adaptive Particle Refinement; Multi-resolution; Quasi-Lagrangian formulations; Riemann solvers; Particle Shifting Technique

1. Introduction

The Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH) method is a numerical method which has recently gained significant popularity as a numerical technique in engineering and, in particular, for fluid mechanics (see, *e.g.* [83, 69, 23]). SPH is particularly advantageous in engineering applications where interfaces are subjected to large deformations, such as violent free-surface or multiphase flows (see, *e.g.* [39]). However, while Adaptive Mesh Refinement has been extensively developed for decades in other well-established numerical methods such as Finite Differences [4], Finite Elements [45] and Finite Volumes [18] and is now widely adopted (see, *e.g.* [31]), the SPH method still lacks a standard Adaptive Particle Refinement (APR) technique to concentrate the computational effort to circumscribed regions of interest [78].

Since the pioneering works in [37, 58, 21], dozens of different techniques have been proposed during the last decade in the SPH literature. However, difficulties arise from both the Lagrangian and meshless characteristics of the method. On the one hand, the meshless spatial operators have to be chosen carefully to account for variable spatial resolution; on the other hand, specific techniques and criteria are required to handle the splitting of Lagrangian particles. In fact, most of the APR or similar multi-resolution techniques

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in SPH can be categorized into three main approaches, essentially based on the selected SPH operators and on the type of multi-resolution technique adopted. These different strategies are detailed in Sec. 2 to contextualize the present work within the existing literature on the topic.

In SPH modeling of free-surface flows, conservative spatial operators are generally preferred thanks to the inherent fulfilment of the dynamic boundary condition, as demonstrated in [14]. In this context sharp variations of the particle size are difficult to handle, since it requires either variable smoothing length operators [21] or the use of buffer regions [12]. Additionally, the use of conservative operators also entails potential limitations in terms of code implementation and parallel efficiency (see, [27, 20] and Sec. 2). By contrast, accurate but non-conservative operators have been employed in [35, 29], allowing sharp variations of the particle size without additional specific treatments. However, the applications of the latter formulations were restricted to internal flows.

Recently in [50], an SPH formulation has been derived featuring an accurate but non-conservative pressure gradient operator inside the fluid domain and a conservative one in the free-surface region. It was made possible thanks to the use of a Particle Shifting Technique (PST) within a quasi-Lagrangian formulation, which allows to maintain the particle distribution regular. Numerical diffusion was needed to reduce the occurrence of spurious high-frequency noise, and it was obtained by means of a Riemann solver. This formulation (called hereinafter RHOD-SPH) has been validated for both internal and free-surface flows, achieving a higher order of convergence than standard schemes with negligible conservation errors. Nevertheless, this approach was restricted to single-resolution cases only.

In the present work, we propose to combine the RHOD-SPH approach with the APR technique adopted in [35, 29] in order to extend the latter to free-surface flows. To this purpose, the adopted Riemann solver is generalized to variable resolution and an adaptation of the PST is introduced. It is worth highlighting that in this work we mainly focus on the formulation. To extend the range of applications, a particle-splitting procedure is used. Since no buffer regions are needed within this framework, the latter is not limited to specific predefined regions, but it is dynamically performed on the basis of different criteria, such as the distance to interfaces. As for particle coalescing, it is not addressed in the present work and will be treated in future works.

The paper is organized as follows: Sec. 2 is dedicated to the description of the current state of the art of APR in the SPH method. After a brief recall of the governing equations in Sec. 3 the extension to APR of the RHOD-SPH approach is presented in Sec. 4 with particular focus on the generalization of Riemann-based diffusive terms and PST. In Sec. 5 the adopted particle-splitting technique is described. Finally, a discussion on the numerical results is provided in Sec. 6 where five benchmarks are studied. Conclusions wrap up the paper.

2. State of the art of Adaptive Particle Refinement in the SPH method for engineering applications

	Approach	Particles Creation	Fluid Interfaces
Oger <i>et al.</i> (2006) [58]	1	No	free-surface
Feldman & Bonet (2007) [21]	1	geom. splitting	free-surface
Vacondio <i>et al.</i> (2013) [79]	1	dyn. splitting	No
Bian <i>et al.</i> (2015) [5]	2	geom. splitting	No
Khorasanizade & Sousa (2017) [35]	3	dyn. splitting	No
Hu <i>et al.</i> (2017) [29]	3	geom. splitting	No
Chiron <i>et al.</i> (2018) [12]	2	geom. splitting	free-surface
Yang & Kong (2019) [90]	1	dyn. splitting	multi-phase
Yang <i>et al.</i> (2021) [91]	1	dyn. splitting	free-surface
Muta & Ramachandran (2022) [55]	1	dyn. splitting	No
Ricci <i>et al.</i> (2024) [67]	2	geom. generation	free-surface
Present work	3	dyn. splitting	free-surface

Table 1: Summary of the main works on APR techniques (called with different names) for engineering applications in the SPH literature; the present work is added for ease of comprehension. The different approaches are described in Sec. 2.1. "geom. splitting" refers to particle-splitting techniques based on predefined (generally circular or rectangular) geometrical domains whereas "dyn. splitting" stands for a refinement based on other criteria (see Sec. 2.2 for details). A specific denomination is used for [67] where the particles are generated in geometrical domains from mass fluxes.

2.1. Major APR techniques

Adaptivity and particle refinement are important topics of the current research on the SPH method. As a matter of fact, "Adaptivity" is one of the five Grand Challenges established by the SPH rEsearch and engineeRing International Community (SPHERIC) [78]. The Adaptive Particle Refinement techniques developed in the SPH method firstly appeared in the astrophysical context (see, *e.g.* [27, 36, 56, 3]) where variable smoothing-length schemes were derived. In the engineering context, most of the current literature on the topic is based on some pioneering works. These works start from the variational approach proposed by Bonet & Lok [6] and extend it to the variable smoothing-length context as, *e.g.*, in Oger *et al.* [58].

More specifically, Lastiwka *et al.* [37] presented a 1D study of SPH operators when particles of different sizes are involved; Oger *et al.* [58] applied a variable smoothing-length scheme to 2D water entry. Finally, the work by Feldman & Bonet [21] is considered the first in the engineering context in which a dynamic particle refinement procedure is proposed and applied to free-surface flows. Most of the recent SPH schemes in the APR context are derived from the approach originally proposed in [21]. It is worth noting that Vila [82] proposed a variable smoothing-length approach within an Arbitrary Lagrangian Eulerian (ALE) framework, which has many similarities with the operators proposed in [21]. The only application of that scheme, to the authors' knowledge, appeared in a conference article [68].

Over the past two decades, numerous studies have been published on APR techniques. Most of these works can be categorized into three major approaches, essentially on the basis of the chosen SPH operators and on the type of APR technique adopted. For the ease of reading, these are summarized in the following and briefly recalled in Tab. 1. Note that many names were used to call these Adaptive Particle Refinement techniques, such as 'Dynamic Refinement', 'Adaptive Meshless', 'Adaptive Resolution', 'Multi-resolution', 'Variable Resolution', or even 'Multiscale'.

Approach n.1: Conservative scheme with mixed interactions

A momentum-conservative formulation is adopted even when particles of different sizes interact, as in [21]. To this purpose the SPH operators have to be modified accordingly, and additional terms accounting for the smoothing-length variations are formally involved. To limit the influence of these

terms, one solution is to keep the spatial variations of the particles size, Δx , small (as in [58, 90]). Otherwise, if large variations of Δx are involved, the ratio $h/\Delta x$ (being h the smoothing length of the SPH interpolation kernel) is modified during particle splitting (or coalescing) in order to keep smooth the spatial variations of h . In particular, $h/\Delta x$ has to be significantly increased when the particle resolution is refined, as in the work by Vacondio *et al.* [79]. In turn, the number of particle neighbors used in SPH operators largely increases, and so the computational cost. This is a key aspect recurring in many other works (see, *e.g.* [65, 90, 55, 10, 28]). It is also important to underline that the use of conservative operators along with variable smoothing length implies the adoption of a “scatter”-type of implementation (see [27]). This can significantly deteriorate the computational efficiency, especially when GPU accelerators are used, as explained by Dominguez *et al.* [20]. Note that, following [58], if the particle size variations are sufficiently small (size ratio between two adjacent particles below 3%) the ratio $h/\Delta x$ can be kept constant with negligible errors.

Approach n.2: Conservative scheme with buffer regions

In order to overcome the limitations of the Approach n.1, other researchers ([2, 5, 12, 67]) proposed a domain decomposition strategy in which the numerical domain is subdivided in sub-domains. Each sub-domain is characterized by a different particle size and particles within have the same size. The ratio $h/\Delta x$ is constant throughout the numerical domain. The different sub-domains communicate with each other by means of suitable buffer regions. This paradigm proved to be very efficient and robust and was successfully applied in a number of different problems (see, *e.g.*, [72, 95, 44, 22, 87]). However, the subdivision in different sub-domains makes this type of APR less flexible with respect to schemes featuring mixed interactions. Additionally, specific treatments are required to handle the buffer regions, thus implying algorithm complexity.

Approach n.3: Non-conservative scheme with mixed interactions

A third approach is the one firstly presented by Khorasanizade & Sousa [35] and Hu *et al.* [29]. In this case, more accurate SPH operators are adopted in the momentum equation. This choice enables direct interaction between particles of different sizes without the need to modify the ratio $h/\Delta x$ or apply specific treatments in the transition zones. This directly reflects on the possible “gather”-type of implementations (following the nomenclature in [27]) which are beneficial for GPU codes [20]. The main drawback of this approach is that momenta are not formally conserved. To the authors’ knowledge this approach has been applied only to internal flows, due to difficulties of these non-conservative schemes to treat the free surface. The present work follows this Approach n.3 and aims at extending it to free-surface flows, as highlighted in Table 1.

Note that for other applications falling outside the scope of the present work, other specific APR techniques have been devised (see, *e.g.* [71, 33, 92]).

2.2. Refinement procedures

As mentioned above, the first work addressing particle splitting is the one by Feldman & Bonet [21]. In this work triangular and hexagonal patterns were considered in two dimensions. Further, a method to determine the optimal smoothing length h and particle size Δx during the particle refinement procedure was presented. The hexagonal pattern was later used by Vacondio *et al.* [79] along with a suitable PST. The same pattern was adopted also by Muta *et al.* [55] and coupled to a coalescing technique in order to obtain a smooth transition of particle size. The optimization method introduced in [21] was extended by Reyes *et al.* [65] for square refinement patterns. The latter was used also in [60, 10] and it has become particularly popular in APR schemes adopting buffer regions (see, *e.g.* [12, 72, 67]). Other refinement patterns were studied in [90, 91]. Further, extensions to 3D were achieved using cubic patterns in, *e.g.* [26, 44], and icosahedron-shaped arrangements in [80].

Once a particle is split into child particles, physical quantities have to be assigned to these novel particles. In [21], the quantities were assigned to the child particles in order to ensure conservation of mass, momenta and kinetic energy. This approach has become the standard one in particle splitting. Incidentally, other

researchers prefer accuracy with respect to conservation by employing a first-order interpolation of velocity and density, as in [29].

Finally, it is worth mentioning also the different refinement criteria adopted in the literature. Most researchers adopt predefined geometrical (generally rectangular or circular) refinement zones [21, 65, 29, 12, 67]. More recently, refinement close to interfaces (solid boundaries, multiphase interfaces and free surfaces) has been proposed, as in [55, 90, 91]. Other works adopted refinement criteria based on the fluid flow fields such as the velocity, vorticity or pressure fields [65, 35, 24, 40]. Note that a refinement criterion based on the interpolation error was also proposed in [70].

3. Governing equations

The fluid is assumed to be a weakly-compressible, Newtonian, isothermal, and barotropic medium. Under these hypotheses the governing equations are the Navier-Stokes equations:

$$\frac{D\rho}{Dt} = -\rho \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}, \quad \rho \frac{D\mathbf{u}}{Dt} = -\nabla P + \mathbf{F}^\mu + \rho \mathbf{f}, \quad \frac{D\mathbf{x}}{Dt} = \mathbf{u} \quad (1)$$

where D/Dt represents the Lagrangian derivative, ρ the fluid density, P the fluid pressure, \mathbf{u} the fluid velocity, \mathbf{f} the external specific volume forces, \mathbf{F}^μ the viscous forces and \mathbf{x} the position of the considered material point. Since the fluid is barotropic, the pressure field and the density field are linked through an equation of state, which is linearized around a reference density value, ρ_0 , due to the hypothesis of weak compressibility. The equation of state and the constraint derived from the latter condition read:

$$P = c_0^2(\rho - \rho_0), \quad c_0 \geq 10 \max\left(\Delta U_{max}, \sqrt{\Delta P_{max}/\rho}\right) \quad (2)$$

where c_0 is the fluid sound speed. ΔU_{max} and ΔP_{max} are, respectively, the maximum velocity and pressure variations within the fluid domain (see, *e.g.* [46]).

4. Generalization of the RHOD-SPH scheme to APR

In [50], the Regularized High-Order Diffusive (RHOD)-SPH scheme has been presented. This scheme is based on four main elements:

- i) a Particle Shifting Technique (PST) to maintain regular particle distributions [57, 42, 30, 64, 34] that lead to accurate interpolation of the SPH operators [62, 78],
- ii) a quasi-Lagrangian formulation to properly introduce this PST in the governing equations [74, 49],
- iii) diffusive terms obtained by means of a Riemann solver [81, 61, 54, 49],
- iv) a switch on the pressure gradient approximation between a renormalized formulation in the bulk of the fluid and a conservative formulation in the free-surface region. The renormalized formulation inside the fluid allows to avoid the Tensile Instability and to increase the order of accuracy of this operator [19]. The conservative formulation in the free-surface region allows to fulfil the dynamic free-surface boundary condition [14].

This RHOD-SPH scheme was developed in a single-resolution context, limiting its application to cases where the zones of interest follow the Lagrangian trajectories of the fluid flow. In the present section, its generalization to APR is presented, that is an extension to be able to handle particles with different size. The procedure used for the particle refinement itself is described in the next section.

Thus, the present section is dedicated to the derivation of the multi-resolution technique for a set of particles of different sizes. In Sec. 4.1 the general framework is recalled. Thanks to this framework, particles of different size can be mixed and evolve together without need for buffer regions or specific treatments, as detailed in Sec. 4.2. Then, the extension to multi-resolution requires the generalization of Riemann solvers, which is provided in Sec. 4.3, and an extension of the PST, given in Sec. 4.4.

4.1. RHOD-SPH framework

Using the RHOD-SPH model described in [50], the Navier-Stokes equations for compressible flows (1) are discretized as follows:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{d\rho_i}{dt} = -\rho_i \langle \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} \rangle_i - \rho_i \langle \nabla \cdot \delta \mathbf{u} \rangle_i + \langle \nabla \cdot (\rho \delta \mathbf{u}) \rangle_i + \Theta_{i,Rie}^\rho \\ \rho_i \frac{d\mathbf{u}_i}{dt} = -\langle \nabla P \rangle_i + \rho_i \mathbf{f}_i + \langle \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{u} \otimes \delta \mathbf{u}) \rangle_i + \mathbf{F}_i^{AD} + \alpha^\mu \mathbf{F}_i^\mu + (1 - \alpha^\mu) \Theta_{i,Rie}^\mathbf{u} \\ \frac{d\mathbf{x}_i}{dt} = \mathbf{u}_i + \delta \mathbf{u}_i, \quad V_i(t) = m_i / \rho_i(t), \quad P_i = c_0^2(\rho_i - \rho_0) \end{array} \right. \quad (3)$$

where subscript i refers to particle i . m_i is the mass of particle i and V_i its volume. $\delta \mathbf{u}$ is the Particle Shifting velocity used to regularize the particles spatial distribution during their motion. In Sec. 4.4 the specific law adopted in the present work is given. The time derivative d/dt used in Eq. (3) indicates a quasi-Lagrangian derivative, *i.e.*:

$$\frac{d(\bullet)}{dt} := \frac{\partial(\bullet)}{\partial t} + \nabla(\bullet) \cdot (\mathbf{u} + \delta \mathbf{u}) = \frac{D(\bullet)}{Dt} + \nabla(\bullet) \cdot \delta \mathbf{u},$$

Since the magnitude of $\delta \mathbf{u}_i$ is small, the hypothesis of particle masses m_i being constant in time is valid (see [74], [1]). The masses are initially set to $m_i = \rho_i(0) V_i(0)$ with $V_i(0)$ and $\rho_i(0)$ the initial particle volumes and densities. The spatial differential operators related to $\delta \mathbf{u}$ are discretized following [74] by:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \langle \nabla \cdot \delta \mathbf{u} \rangle_i = \sum_j (\delta \mathbf{u}_j - \delta \mathbf{u}_i) \cdot \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j \\ \langle \nabla \cdot (\rho \delta \mathbf{u}) \rangle_i = \sum_j (\rho_i \delta \mathbf{u}_i + \rho_j \delta \mathbf{u}_j) \cdot \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j \\ \langle \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{u} \otimes \delta \mathbf{u}) \rangle_i = \sum_j (\rho_i \mathbf{u}_i \otimes \delta \mathbf{u}_i + \rho_j \mathbf{u}_j \otimes \delta \mathbf{u}_j) \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j \end{array} \right. \quad (4)$$

W is the \mathcal{C}^2 -Wendland kernel function [86] adopted and subscript j indicates the neighboring particles to particle i . The notation $W_{ij} = W(\|\mathbf{x}_j - \mathbf{x}_i\|, R_i)$ is used and details about kernel radii R_i adopted with APR are given in Sec. 4.2. The velocity divergence is expressed as:

$$\langle \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} \rangle_i = \sum_j (\mathbf{u}_j - \mathbf{u}_i) \cdot \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j \quad (5)$$

The pressure gradient approximation depends on the distance to the free surface (see Fig. 1 and [50] for details) and reads:

$$\langle \nabla P \rangle_i = \begin{cases} \mathbb{L}_i \sum_j (P_j - P_i) \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j & \text{if } i \in \mathcal{I} \text{ and } \Gamma_i \geq \Gamma_{th} \\ \sum_j (P_j + P_i) \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

where Γ_i is the Shepard value defined as:

$$\Gamma_i = \sum_j \Gamma_{ij}; \quad \Gamma_{ij} = W_{ij} V_j \quad (7)$$

and Γ_{th} is a threshold value set to $\Gamma_{th} = 0.85$ in this work. \mathbb{L}_i is the renormalization matrix [63]:

$$\mathbb{L}_i = \left[\sum_j (\mathbf{x}_j - \mathbf{x}_i) \otimes \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j \right]^{-1} \quad (8)$$

ensuring the exact gradient approximation of a linear pressure field. This property being valid for any particle distribution, it represents the key point of the present scheme with APR, as previously noted by Hu *et al.* in [29]. Note that the choice of a non-symmetric formula for the pressure gradient entails the removal of the kernel function dependency on the smoothing length of neighboring particles. As already mentioned, this allows a “gather”-type implementation of the scheme which has significant advantages when GPU acceleration is employed [20]. For the divergence operators $\langle \nabla \cdot (\rho \delta \mathbf{u}) \rangle_i$, $\langle \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{u} \otimes \delta \mathbf{u}) \rangle_i$ and \mathbf{F}_i^{AD} we preferred not to introduce an h -dependency which would allow the symmetry of these operators to be preserved. With this choice we can maintain the “gather”-type implementation.

Figure 1: Definition of the free-surface region and inner particles along with the related pressure gradient approximations. Left plot: pressure gradient approximations depending on the distance to the free-surface, with \mathbb{L}_i the renormalization matrix defined in Eq. (8). Right plot: sketch of the free-surface region defined as the union of free-surface particles \mathcal{F} and vicinity particles \mathcal{V} which are the particles having at least one free-surface particle within their kernel support. Inner particles \mathcal{I} are particles that do not interact with free-surface particles. Free-surface particles are determined following [47].

\mathbf{F}_i^{AD} refers to the acoustic damper term which reads:

$$\mathbf{F}_i^{AD} = \alpha^{AD} \rho_0 c_0 h_i \sum_j (D_j + D_i) \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j \quad ; \quad D_k = \sum_l (\mathbf{u}_l - \mathbf{u}_k) \cdot \nabla_k W_{kl} V_l \quad (9)$$

with ρ_0 the fluid density at rest, h_i the smoothing length associated to particle i and $\alpha^{AD} = 1$ to allow the largest possible dissipation of the acoustic waves without affecting the time step [76]. \mathbf{F}_i^μ stands for the viscous forces and the Monaghan & Gingold formulation [53] is used:

$$\mathbf{F}_i^\mu = \mu \sum_j 2(d+2) \pi_{ij} \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j, \quad \pi_{ij} = \frac{(\mathbf{u}_j - \mathbf{u}_i) \cdot (\mathbf{x}_j - \mathbf{x}_i)}{\|\mathbf{x}_j - \mathbf{x}_i\|^2} \quad (10)$$

where μ is the dynamic viscosity coefficient and d is the spatial dimension. For studying low Reynolds numbers within the present framework, a higher-order Laplacian velocity operator should be used as, *e.g.* in [29], which is left to future work.

The symbols $\Theta_{i,Rie}^\rho$ and $\Theta_{i,Rie}^u$ in Eq. (3) denote the numerical diffusive terms stemming from the use of Riemann solvers, their derivation in the APR context being detailed in Sec. 4.3 (their expression are given in Eqs. (23) and (24) respectively). $\alpha^\mu = \{1 \text{ if } \mu \neq 0; 0 \text{ otherwise}\}$ stands for a mutual exclusion term. Indeed, in the present work we remarked that considering $\Theta_{i,Rie}^u$ in addition to viscous forces \mathbf{F}_i^μ results in excessive dissipation. Therefore, when viscous flows are considered the Riemann-based diffusive term in the

momentum equation is disabled by setting $\alpha^\mu = 1$. This is analogous to what is commonly done when using δ -SPH formulations for simulating viscous flows (see, *e.g.* [75]). Note that reducing the numerical viscosity induced by $\Theta_{i,Rie}^\mu$ represents an active topic of research within the SPH community (see, *e.g.* [88, 93]).

Solid boundary conditions are modelled using mirrored ghost particles (see, *e.g.* [41, 16, 17, 59]). In Secs. 6.3 and 6.5 the forces exerted by the fluid on solid bodies are used as a validation feature. In these cases the forces are computed following [7]. Finally, the scheme (3) is integrated in time by using a 4th-order Runge-Kutta scheme and the following Courant-Friedrichs-Lewy numbers are adopted:

$$\Delta t = \min_i \left(CFL_h \frac{R_i}{c_0}, \frac{CFL_h R_i}{\alpha^{AD} c_0}, CFL_\mu \frac{\rho_0 R_i^2}{\mu} \right); \quad CFL_h = 0.5; \quad CFL_\mu = 0.025 \quad (11)$$

Note that, for the Reynolds number range and coefficient α^{AD} adopted in the present work, the acoustic constraint is always the most restrictive.

4.2. APR approach adopted in the present work

As stressed in Sec. 2, different approaches exist in the SPH literature to deal with APR, these approaches being mainly driven by the SPH operators used. The adoption of an accurate pressure gradient within the RHOD-SPH scheme enables the usage of Approach n.3 mentioned in Sec. 2. This approach allows for large variations in particle size without requiring buffer regions or variations of the $h/\Delta x$ ratio. Furthermore, in the present work this approach extends to free-surface flows thanks to the conservative form of the pressure gradient operator (6) in the free-surface region.

Each particle i has its own characteristic size Δx_i and kernel support radius R_i , with a fixed ratio $R_i/\Delta x_i$ for all particles; a ratio $R_i/\Delta x_i = 4$ is used all along the present work. As shown in Fig. 2, particles of significantly different size are mixed and interact with each other without the need of any predefined geometrical refinement box or buffer region.

Figure 2: Illustration of the present APR approach on a dam-break test case. Particles of different size Δx_i are represented with different colours. Δx_{min} stands for the minimum size in the simulation. A close-up is provided in the right plot where three particles i_1 , i_2 and i_4 of different size are identified, with their kernel support and radius.

4.3. Generalization of Riemann-based diffusive terms with APR

In [50], Riemann-based diffusive terms have been described for single resolution. Their extension to the APR context is derived in the next subsections. Before going into details about this extension, we briefly recall the main steps of the procedure for single resolution:

1. Considering a fictitious interface located at mid-distance between particles i and j , and determining the left and right states (ϕ_L and ϕ_R , respectively) at this fictitious interface using piecewise linear reconstructions and limitation.
2. Obtaining the Riemann problem solution \mathbf{u}_E and P_E at this interface by using a Riemann solver.
3. Manipulating the velocity divergence and pressure gradient SPH approximations to make appear explicitly the values ϕ_{ij} obtained by a linear approximation at this interface; in [50], values

corresponding to the arithmetic means $\frac{\mathbf{u}_i + \mathbf{u}_j}{2}$ and $\frac{P_i + P_j}{2}$ were chosen as initially proposed in [61]. Replacing these values by the Riemann problem solution, thus giving the diffusive terms obtained by means of a Riemann solver.

When particles of different sizes are considered, the fictitious interface is not necessarily located at mid-distance between particles i and j and the whole procedure has to be generalized, which is the aim of the next three subsections.

4.3.1. Left and right states for the Riemann problem at the fictitious interface \mathbf{x}_{ij}

Figure 3: Sketch of fictitious interface \mathbf{x}_{ij} between particles i and j . Particle i (resp. j) is located in \mathbf{x}_i (resp. \mathbf{x}_j), of characteristic size Δx_i (resp. Δx_j), of weight $\omega_i = \frac{\Delta x_i}{\Delta x_i + \Delta x_j}$ (resp. $\omega_j = \frac{\Delta x_j}{\Delta x_i + \Delta x_j}$) and of value ϕ_i (resp. ϕ_j). ϕ_L (resp. ϕ_R) represents the left state (resp. right state) obtained by reconstruction/limitation, while $\phi_{ij} = (1 - \omega_i)\phi_i + (1 - \omega_j)\phi_j$ stands for the linear interpolation of ϕ at position \mathbf{x}_{ij} .

With APR, as sketched in Fig. 3 the fictitious interface position \mathbf{x}_{ij} is chosen as:

$$\mathbf{x}_{ij} = \mathbf{x}_i + \omega_i(\mathbf{x}_j - \mathbf{x}_i) = \mathbf{x}_j + \omega_j(\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_j) \quad , \quad \omega_i = \frac{\Delta x_i}{\Delta x_i + \Delta x_j} \quad , \quad \omega_j = \frac{\Delta x_j}{\Delta x_i + \Delta x_j} \quad (12)$$

Note that by construction $\omega_i + \omega_j = 1$. For a $i - j$ interface located at \mathbf{x}_{ij} , the determination of the left state ϕ_L of the Riemann problem first consists in computing two slopes $\Delta\phi_i^1$ and $\Delta\phi_i^2$:

$$\Delta\phi_i^1 = \frac{\phi_j - \phi_i}{\|\mathbf{x}_j - \mathbf{x}_i\|} \quad \text{and} \quad \Delta\phi_i^2 = \langle \nabla\phi_i \rangle_i^{\mathcal{L}} \cdot \mathbf{n}_{ij}, \quad (13)$$

where

$$\mathbf{n}_{ij} = \frac{\mathbf{x}_j - \mathbf{x}_i}{\|\mathbf{x}_j - \mathbf{x}_i\|} \quad \text{and} \quad \langle \nabla\phi \rangle_i^{\mathcal{L}} = \mathbb{L}_i \sum_j (\phi_j - \phi_i) \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j \quad \text{with } \mathbb{L}_i \text{ defined in Eq. (8)}. \quad (14)$$

Then, as proposed in [81, 54] the retained slope reads:

$$\Delta\phi_i = \begin{cases} \frac{2\Delta\phi_i^1\Delta\phi_i^2}{\Delta\phi_i^1 + \Delta\phi_i^2} & \text{if } \Delta\phi_i^2\Delta\phi_i^1 > 0 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

Precisely, for slopes $\Delta\phi_i^1$ and $\Delta\phi_i^2$ of same sign, their harmonic mean is considered while a constant reconstruction is employed otherwise. Finally, and following the same procedure for the right state, the left and right states are defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_L &= \phi_i + \omega_i \Delta\phi_i \|\mathbf{x}_j - \mathbf{x}_i\| \\ \phi_R &= \phi_j + \omega_j \Delta\phi_j \|\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_j\| \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

4.3.2. The Primitive Variable Riemann Solver

As in [49, 50], the approximate Riemann solver usually named Primitive Variable Riemann Solver (PVRS) (see *e.g.* [77]) is used, since it provides results that are very close to those predicted by the exact Riemann solver, but at a lower computational cost. The primitive variables being ρ and \mathbf{u} , the related pressure P is determined through Eq. (2). Since a constant speed of sound is imposed by (2), *i.e.* $c_L = c_R = c_0$, the Riemann problem solutions read:

$$\mathbf{u}_E = \left[\frac{\rho_R u_R + \rho_L u_L}{\rho_R + \rho_L} + \frac{P_L - P_R}{c_0(\rho_L + \rho_R)} \right] \cdot \mathbf{n}_{ij} \quad (17)$$

$$(18)$$

$$P_E = \frac{\rho_R P_L + \rho_L P_R}{\rho_R + \rho_L} + \frac{\rho_R \rho_L c_0 (u_L - u_R)}{\rho_R + \rho_L}. \quad (19)$$

4.3.3. Diffusive terms obtained by means of Riemann solver

In order to express the diffusive terms obtained by means of Riemann solver, it is first necessary to manipulate the velocity divergence and pressure gradient SPH operators to make appear explicitly the linear interpolation of the considered physical quantities ϕ at the interface \mathbf{x}_{ij} , *i.e.*

$$\phi_{ij} = (1 - \omega_i)\phi_i + (1 - \omega_j)\phi_j \quad (20)$$

as also sketched in Fig. 3. For the sake of brevity, the whole derivation is given for the diffusive term appearing in the continuity equation $\Theta_{i,Rie}^\rho$, a similar derivation enable to express $\Theta_{i,Rie}^u$.

To express $\Theta_{i,Rie}^\rho$, the first step consists in writing the velocity divergence (5) as:

$$\langle \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} \rangle_i = \sum_j (\mathbf{u}_j - \mathbf{u}_i) \cdot \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j = \sum_j 2[(1 - \omega_i)\mathbf{u}_i + (1 - \omega_j)\mathbf{u}_j + \mathcal{R}_{ij}] \cdot \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j \quad (21)$$

with \mathcal{R}_{ij} the remaining term equal to $\mathcal{R}_{ij} = -\left(\frac{3}{2} - \omega_i\right)\mathbf{u}_i - \left(\frac{1}{2} - \omega_j\right)\mathbf{u}_j$. Then, the Riemann diffusive term is introduced within the scheme by replacing the quantity $(1 - \omega_i)\mathbf{u}_i + (1 - \omega_j)\mathbf{u}_j$ in Eq. (21) by \mathbf{u}_E the Riemann problem solution. It leads to:

$$\langle \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} \rangle_i + \Theta_{i,Rie}^\rho = \sum_j 2[\mathbf{u}_E + \mathcal{R}_{ij}] \cdot \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j \quad (22)$$

and consequently $\Theta_{i,Rie}^\rho$ is expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned}\Theta_{i,Rie}^\rho &= \sum_j 2 [\mathbf{u}_E + \mathcal{R}_{ij}] \cdot \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j - \langle \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} \rangle_i \\ &= \sum_j 2 [\mathbf{u}_E + \mathcal{R}_{ij} - (1 - \omega_i) \mathbf{u}_i - (1 - \omega_j) \mathbf{u}_j - \mathcal{R}_{ij}] \cdot \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j \\ &= \sum_j 2 (\mathbf{u}_E - [(1 - \omega_i) \mathbf{u}_i + (1 - \omega_j) \mathbf{u}_j]) \cdot \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j.\end{aligned}\quad (23)$$

The diffusion term in the momentum equation $\Theta_{i,Rie}^u$ is derived using the same procedure and reads:

$$\Theta_{i,Rie}^u = \begin{cases} -\mathbb{L}_i \sum_j \theta_{ij}^u \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j & \text{if } i \in \mathcal{I} \text{ \& } \Gamma_i > 0.95 \\ -\sum_j \theta_{ij}^u \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}; \theta_{ij}^u = 2 \{P_E - [(1 - \omega_i) P_i + (1 - \omega_j) P_j]\} \quad (24)$$

Notably, for interactions between particles of same size (*i.e.* with $\omega_i = \omega_j = \frac{1}{2}$) the Riemann-based diffusive terms derived in the present work are equivalent to those in [50]. Note that Eq. (22) can be used for implementing the whole term $\langle \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} \rangle_i + \Theta_{i,Rie}^\rho$ appearing in Eq. (3) by saving few CPU time, an equivalent formulation being easy to find for implementing the term $\langle \nabla P \rangle_i + \Theta_{i,Rie}^u$.

4.4. Particle Shifting Technique with APR

Using a PST is common in SPH to maintain regular particles distribution, and becomes crucial when dealing with APR [12, 89, 48]. When mixed interactions are considered, PST has to be modified (see *e.g.* [79]). In the present section, the PST velocity retained for multi-resolution is detailed. It is based on the pioneer work of Lind *et al.* about PSTs based on Fick's law of concentration [42], adapted to weakly-compressible assumption by Oger *et al.* [59], improved in [51] in terms of consistency and invariances, with the limitation derived in [49] dedicated to quasi-Lagrangian formulations. The obtained PST velocity $\delta \mathbf{u}_i$ was used in the RHOD-SPH framework in [50] and its generic formulation is recalled in Sec. 4.4.1. For more accurate results in multi-resolution, the gradient of concentration ∇C_i is slightly modified with respect to [50], and details are provided in Sec. 4.4.2.

4.4.1. PST velocity

As all PSTs based on Fick's law, the first step consists in computing a non-dimensional vector \mathbf{J}_i pointing towards zones of low concentration of particles, and, as in [51], it is expressed as:

$$\mathbf{J}_i = -R_i \nabla C_i, \quad (25)$$

∇C_i being the gradient of concentration, detailed below in Sec. 4.4.2. To ensure the kinematic free-surface condition, \mathbf{J}_i has to be projected in the tangential direction. Different treatments have been proposed to this purpose in the literature (see *e.g.* [32, 75, 85, 74, 51]). In the present work, the treatment proposed in [51] is retained and consists in a progressive projection in the free-surface region. The projected vector reads:

$$\mathbf{J}_i^\perp = \mathbf{J}_i - \sigma_i (\mathbf{J}_i \cdot \tilde{\mathbf{n}}_i) \tilde{\mathbf{n}}_i \quad (26)$$

with $\tilde{\mathbf{n}}_i$ the normal vector in the free-surface region and σ_i the projection function, both defined in [51]. For inner fluid particles $\tilde{\mathbf{n}}_i = \mathbf{0}$. Finally, the PST velocity $\delta \mathbf{u}_i$ is computed as follows:

$$\delta \mathbf{u}_i = \mathbf{J}_i^\perp \min \left(a_i U_i^{char}; \quad b_i \frac{R_i U_i^{char}}{\Delta x_i \|\mathbf{J}_i^\perp\|}; \quad \frac{\epsilon}{2\Delta t \|\mathbf{J}_i^\perp \cdot \nabla \Gamma_i\|} \right); \quad \nabla \Gamma_i = \sum_j \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j \quad (27)$$

with (i) $U_i^{char} = \max_j \left(\left| (\mathbf{u}_j - \mathbf{u}_i) \cdot \frac{(\mathbf{x}_j - \mathbf{x}_i)}{\|\mathbf{x}_j - \mathbf{x}_i\|} \right| \right)$ the characteristic PST velocity, (ii) $a_i = 0.5$ the PST coefficient, (iii) $b_i = 0.05$ a protection against strong values of \mathbf{J}_i^\perp , and (iv) ϵ the maximum variation of density due to the shifting enabled during one time-step Δt . The derivation of the latter term has been performed in [49] and in the present work the limitation is set to $\epsilon = 5.10^{-4}$.

4.4.2. Gradient of concentration ∇C_i in APR

While $\nabla \Gamma_i$ was used as a basis vector for the packing algorithm [15], in the PST context a more "local" gradient of concentration is generally preferred. In [42], Lind *et al.* proposed to use:

$$\nabla C_i^{L. et al.} = \sum_j \left[1 + 0.2 \left(\frac{W_{ij}}{W(dx)} \right)^4 \right] \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j \quad ; \quad dx = \Delta x \quad (28)$$

with dx the targeted inter-particles size, *i.e.* $dx = \Delta x$ in single resolution. Therefore, when two particles i and j are closer than the characteristic distance Δx , their contribution in the computation of $\nabla C_i^{L. et al.}$ is increased with respect to $\nabla \Gamma_i$, as sketched in Fig. 4.

Figure 4: Effect of the non-linear term of Eq. 28 in function of y

In APR, the targeted inter-particles size becomes $dx_{ij} = \frac{\Delta x_i + \Delta x_j}{2}$. Consequently, the gradient of concentration has to be adapted to become the basis vector of Eq. (25) as:

$$\nabla C_i = \sum_j \left[1 + 0.2 \left(\frac{W_{ij}}{W(dx_{ij})} \right)^4 \right] \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j \quad ; \quad dx_{ij} = \frac{\Delta x_i + \Delta x_j}{2} \quad (29)$$

It is worth mentioning that Eqs. (29) and (28) are equivalent in the single-resolution context.

5. Refinement procedure and criteria

To enlarge the range of applications achievable with the present multi-resolution technique, a refinement procedure is employed, divided in two steps. The first step consists in determining particles that require a refinement. This task is performed by considering some criteria and a particle that fulfils these criteria is marked as "refinement required". The criteria are determined at the end of the current time-step $t + \Delta t$ (precisely during the last stage of the time integration scheme). In the second step the particles marked as "refinement required" enters in a refinement procedure before starting the following time step. Criteria and refinement procedure are detailed in the following sections.

5.1. Refinement procedure

As highlighted in Sec. 2, different refinement procedures have been proposed in the SPH literature, both regarding the refinement pattern and the assignment of the physical quantities to the newly generated particles. In the present work, a particle i of size Δx_i marked as "refinement required" is split in 2^D fine particles (called child particles) with D the spatial dimension. In the present work only 2D cases are treated. Therefore, four child particles are created during the refinement procedure, noted i_{c1} , i_{c2} , i_{c3} and i_{c4} as represented in Fig. 5. As in [12] the refinement pattern is a square of length $\Delta x_i/2$, the characteristic distances of the child particles (size, radius, smoothing length) being half the ones of the particle i . The refinement pattern is oriented to maximize the minimum inter-particle distance once the refinement completed, as sketched in Fig. 5.

Figure 5: Sketch of the refinement position pattern for a particle i of size Δx_i . (a) Initial configuration: the black line indicates the direction to the closest neighbour particle; (b) particle i is split into 4 particles of size $\Delta x_i/2$ located on a circle of radius $R_i^{pat} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \frac{\Delta x_i}{2}$. (c) The refinement pattern is a square with side length $\Delta x_i/2$, oriented in alignment with the black line in order to maximize particle spacing upon completion of the refinement. (d) Final configuration: child particles i_{c1} to i_{c4} are created and original particle i is deleted.

Regarding the assignment of the physical quantities to the child particles, different strategies have been studied in the literature, as stressed in Sec. 2. After some tests, we remark that conversely to [29] and in agreement with [21] better results are obtained with a strategy ensuring conservation of mass, momenta and kinetic energy. To ensure both linear momentum and kinetic energy conservation, the velocity of the child particles is the original velocity:

$$\mathbf{u}_{i_{c1}} = \mathbf{u}_{i_{c2}} = \mathbf{u}_{i_{c3}} = \mathbf{u}_{i_{c4}} = \mathbf{u}_i.$$

To ensure both mass and angular momentum conservation, the mass of particle i is equally distributed on the child particles:

$$m_{i_{c1}} = m_{i_{c2}} = m_{i_{c3}} = m_{i_{c4}} = \frac{m_i}{4}.$$

Following [29], the pressure field is linearly projected and the volume are chosen to ensure equal distribution of mass, that is as:

$$P_{i_{ck}} = P_i + \langle \nabla P \rangle_i^{\mathcal{L}} \cdot (\mathbf{x}_{i_{ck}} - \mathbf{x}_i) \quad ; \quad \rho_{i_{ck}} = P_{i_{ck}}/c_0^2 + \rho_0 \quad ; \quad V_{i_{ck}} = \frac{1}{\rho_{i_{ck}}} \frac{V_i \rho_i}{4} \quad ; \quad k = 1, \dots, 4$$

with $\langle \nabla P \rangle_i^{\mathcal{L}}$ computed following Eq. (14) with $\phi_i = P_i$.

5.2. Refinement criteria

In the present paper a particle i is marked as "refinement required" if one of the following criteria is fulfilled:

- (1) i interacts with a "grandchild" particle, *i.e.* if $\exists j \in \mathcal{D}(i) : \Delta x_j = \Delta x_i/4$, where $\mathcal{D}(i)$ is the set of particles located inside the kernel support of particle i .
- (2) i is isolated in a field of smaller particles, *i.e.* if
$$\sum_{j \in \mathcal{D}(i) : \Delta x_j \geq \Delta x_i} \Gamma_{ij} < 2\Gamma_{ii}.$$
- (3) i belongs to the free-surface region, *i.e.* i interacts with a free-surface particle.
- (4) i is close a solid boundary, *i.e.* the kernel support of i intersects a solid panel.
- (5) i has a physical value that is higher than a threshold value, *i.e.* if $\phi_i > \phi_{th}$.

Criteria (1) \rightarrow (2) are always activated whereas criteria (3) \rightarrow (5) depend on the targeted zone of interest and, therefore, on the targeted application. The criterion (1) stands for a stability criterion and is employed to prevent kernel issues of "grandchild" particles. Indeed, since a "gather"-type of interactions is retained in this work along with a ratio $\frac{R_i}{\Delta x_i} = 4$, the presence of a particle with size $4\Delta x_i$ in the kernel support would be an excessive coarseness in the summation integral and could result in an artificial void. Note that using such a criterion is a common practice in other numerical methods, like in Finite Volume method to avoid a too large size ratio between two adjacent cells (see *e.g.* [84]). The criterion (2) is employed since there is no gain in keeping a particle surrounded by finer particles. Such a particle is then refined in order to retrieve a particle field of the same size, and the criterion is based on a shepard approximation where Γ_{ij} is defined in Eq. (7). Note that in the present work, a minimum particle size Δx_{min} is imposed in the simulation, which is fixed prior to the simulation. Therefore Δx_{min} can not be exceeded. To this end, a necessary condition for i to be refined is that it is sufficiently coarse to handle another refinement, *i.e.* if $\Delta x_i/2 > \Delta x_{min}$.

Criteria (3) and (4) can be activated depending on the zones of interest of the targeted application and, if several bodies are involved, the criterion (4) can be activated only on selected bodies. It induces a thin zone of size $2R$ in which particles are all of same size $\Delta x = \Delta x_{min}$ and, thanks to the criterion (1), this is repeated for the successive refinement levels, as sketched in Fig. 6. Note that the initial particle setup is chosen to naturally ensure the criteria in order to avoid a refinement cascade at the beginning of the simulation.

The aim of APR is to retrieve the same results of those obtained with single-resolution, but at a lower CPU cost. For some applications criteria (3) and (4) are not sufficient, and the criterion (5) is activated in such cases. Here a simple criterion is used: it is based on the pressure value and a particle i is refined when a threshold pressure is exceeded. This threshold pressure depends on the application and consequently the criterion does not present a generic feature. Deriving such generic criteria is left to future works, but the presence of the criterion (5) shows that the present formulation can be also used in combination with criteria depending on the field quantities.

Figure 6: Example of spatial resolutions obtained for a flow past an immersed cylinder when criteria (1) \rightarrow (3) are activated. Criterion (4) is activated around the cylinder and disabled at the bottom part of the tank. Criterion (5) is not activated.

6. Numerical discussion

This section is dedicated to the discussion of the numerical results. Five two-dimensional benchmarks are selected. The results obtained are compared to both reference results and results obtained in single-resolution.

As a first test, a hydrostatic case is considered. It acts as a demonstrative case to show the capability of Approach n.3 to deal with large Δx variations with a “gather”-type of interpolation and without the need for adapting the smoothing length h .

The second test case is the classic rotating square patch [38]. It represents a suitable and challenging case for studying the behavior of the proposed scheme when free-surface particles are continuously generated in the free-surface region subjected to large deformations. To the best knowledge of the authors it is the first time that this case is studied in the APR context.

The third test case consists in a water entry of a V-shaped body. Due to the large dimension of the tank, the refinement is essential in this test case and it is therefore often used to validate APR techniques in the SPH community. It represents also a relevant test case to study the proposed scheme when particles are continuously generated close to solid boundaries.

The fourth benchmark is a dam-break case and represents one of the most popular cases in the SPH community. In the APR context, dam-break cases were studied with Approach n.1 [91] and Approach n.2 [12]. In the present work, the refinement is activated in the free-surface region, and this case is considered here to address the robustness of the proposed scheme in presence of multiple free-surface reconnections.

Finally, a flow past an immersed cylinder is considered. Flows past obstacles are classic cases in the APR context and have been analysed using all three approaches (see, *e.g.* [55, 73, 29]). Here, one of the cases introduced in [8] is investigated where the cylinder is placed below the free surface with a Froude number $Fr = 1$. Vortical structures being generated by both the cylinder and free-surface deformations, the refinement is activated both in the free-surface region and close to the cylinder.

6.1. Hydrostatic test case

Figure 7: Hydrostatic test case. Initial setup of the case. A zoom is provided in the right plot to highlight the effect of the packing algorithm [15].

In this case a fluid column of height H , width $L = 0.5H$ and nominal density ρ_0 is placed inside a tank of same width and of height $2H$ as depicted in the left plot of Fig. 7. Two spatial resolutions are

used depending on the relative position to a curve of equation $y = 0.25H \sin(\frac{2\pi x}{0.25H}) + 0.5H$, with the origin $[x = 0 ; y = 0]$ located at the bottom left corner of the tank. Above that curve the particle size Δx is set to $\frac{H}{\Delta x} = 200$ whereas on the bottom part $\frac{H}{\Delta x} = 100$. The packing algorithm presented in [15] is applied independently within each sub-domain to properly initialize the particle distribution. A zoom around a multi-resolution zone is provided in the right plot of Fig. 7 to highlight the effect of this procedure. The initial velocity and pressure are respectively $\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{0}$ and $P = \rho_0 g(H - y)$ where g stands for the gravity magnitude. The speed of sound is set to $c_0 = 10\sqrt{gH}$ following the weakly-compressible assumption (2). The reference scales are the length H , the time $\sqrt{H/g}$, the pressure $\rho_0 gH$ and the energy $V\rho_0 gH$ with V the volume of fluid. Criteria (4) and (5) are not considered. Consequently, the refinement procedure is never activated for this test case. As stressed in Sec. 2, using Approach n.1 with these large Δx variations would require smooth variations of h , whereas Approach n.2 seems hardly applicable due to the geometrical shapes of the refined zones. Consequently, this benchmark is a demonstrative case to show the benefits of Approach n.3, *i.e.* using the accurate pressure gradient approximation defined in Eq. (6) with mixed interactions. To validate quantitatively the present formulation, results obtained with single-resolution are also given.

Figure 8: Hydrostatic test case. Left: temporal evolution of the kinetic energy \mathcal{E}_k obtained with the present APR, compared to those obtained in single resolutions $H/\Delta x = 100$ and $H/\Delta x = 200$. Right: pressure obtained with the present APR scheme at $t\sqrt{g/H} = 100$.

In Fig.8, the results of the present APR scheme are reported in terms of kinetic energy and pressure field. Specifically, the temporal evolution of the kinetic energy \mathcal{E}_k is plotted in the left plot, and compared to single-resolution cases. At $t\sqrt{g/H} = 100$, the kinetic energy obtained with the APR scheme remains below 10^{-12} of the reference energy $V\rho_0 gH$. This result reflects the small variations in the particle displacement occurring during the simulation. Indeed, the particle displacement at $t\sqrt{g/H} = 100$ is such that $\sqrt{\frac{\sum_i \|\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_i^0\|^2 V_i}{V}} < 0.015 \Delta x_{min}$, being \mathbf{x}_i^0 the position of particle i at $t = 0$. In other words, at the end of the simulation, a characteristic displacement of 1.5% Δx_{min} is noted with respect to the initial position. The oscillations of \mathcal{E}_k occurring in the first part of the simulations are due to the transfer between compressible and kinetic energy inherent to the weakly-compressible assumption. These oscillations are progressively damped thanks to the acoustic damper term, and once the acoustic wave is fully dissipated, the kinetic energy retained by the APR scheme falls between the values observed in the single-resolution cases.

As shown in the right plot of Fig.8, an accurate pressure field is obtained. Precisely, it converges towards the analytical solution of the compressible hydrostatic pressure $P_{an} = \rho_0 c_0^2 \left[e^{(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_{FS}) \cdot \mathbf{g} / c_0^2} - 1 \right]$ where \mathbf{x}_{FS}

is a point located on the free-surface. At $t\sqrt{g/H} = 100$, the maximum error with respect to P_{an} is such that $\|P - P_{an}\|_{\infty} = 3.6 \times 10^{-4} \rho_0 g H$.

6.2. Rotating square patch at $Re = 2000$

In the present section, a classical benchmark is studied where large free-surface deformations are involved [13, 38, 32, 74, 50]. It consists in an initial square fluid domain of length L , in which the velocity field is initialized with an uniform angular velocity $-\sigma_0$; the center of rotation is the center of the square. The initial velocity and pressure are

$$\begin{cases} u_x = \sigma_0 y \\ u_y = -\sigma_0 x \\ p = \rho_0 \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{-32\sigma_0^2}{mn\pi^2 [(n\pi/L)^2 + (m\pi/L)^2]} \sin(m\pi x/L) \sin(n\pi y/L) \end{cases} \quad (30)$$

and the reference variables are the length L , the time $1/\sigma_0$, the velocity $L\sigma_0$, the pressure $\rho_0 L^2 \sigma_0^2$, the vorticity $2\sigma_0$ and the initial kinetic energy \mathcal{E}_k^0 . The speed of sound is chosen as $c_0 = 10 L\sigma_0$. The pressure is negative in all the fluid domain with an adverse pressure gradient at the free-surface. Therefore, Rayleigh-Taylor instability is expected to appear. To prevent this instabilities, it is necessary to add a sort of viscosity to the fluid, either artificial or physical. As in [50] we preferred the latter choice to avoid a dependence of the viscosity on the spatial resolution (as for the artificial viscosity). The corresponding Reynolds number is chosen as in [50] as $Re = 2000$ with $Re = \rho_0 L^2 \sigma_0 / \mu$. The particles are initialized as represented in Fig. 9, that is with a spatial resolution $L/\Delta x = 200$ inside a disk of radius $R_{200}/L = 0.44$, $L/\Delta x = 400$ inside a circular ring of internal and external radii $R_{200}/L = 0.44$ and $R_{400}/L = 0.48$ respectively, and $L/\Delta x = 800$ elsewhere. The particle packing algorithm [15] is used for a better initial particles distribution.

Figure 9: Rotating square patch at $Re = 2000$. Initial particles distribution: $L/\Delta x = 200$ inside a disk of radius $R_{200}/L = 0.44$, $L/\Delta x = 400$ inside a circular ring of internal and external radii $R_{200}/L = 0.44$ and $R_{400}/L = 0.48$ respectively, and $L/\Delta x = 800$ elsewhere.

Refinement criteria (1) \rightarrow (3) are used. This test case represents a suitable and challenging benchmark for validating the refinement procedure in the free-surface region as the free surface is subjected to large deformations and, therefore, new particles are continuously generated (see right plots of Fig. 10). The vorticity field at different instant is plotted in the left part of Fig. 10 and displays a continuous behaviour, even in zones of large Δx variations. The free-surface shape is compared to the one obtained in single-resolution $L/\Delta x = 800$, the latter having already been validated against reference results in [50]. A good agreement is found all along the simulation. Only small differences are observed from t/σ_0 in the patch centre which are acceptable in light of the fluid flow evolution complexity.

Figure 10: Rotating square patch at $Re = 2000$. Left: vorticity field obtained at different instants $t/\sigma_0 = 2, 4$ (from top to bottom). Right: spatial resolution Δx_i at the same instants. In the left plot, the black line stands for the free-surface obtained with a single-resolution SPH $L/\Delta x = 800$.

Figure 11: Rotating square patch at $Re = 2000$. Left: vorticity field obtained at different instants $t/\sigma_0 = 6, 8$ (from top to bottom). Right: spatial resolution Δx_i at the same instants. In the left plot, the black line stands for the free-surface obtained with a single-resolution SPH $L/\Delta x = 800$.

This good agreement is confirmed in Fig. 12 where the temporal evolution of the kinetic energy is compared to the one obtained with the single-resolutions $L/\Delta x = 200$, $L/\Delta x = 400$ and $L/\Delta x = 800$. Since the APR simulation is composed of particles of these different sizes, the expected behaviour of an accurate APR scheme is an energy dissipation located somewhere between the one obtained with the single-resolutions $L/\Delta x = 200$ and $L/\Delta x = 800$. In fact, the kinetic energy is close to the one obtained with $L/\Delta x = 400$, with a relative error of 0.36% with respect to $L/\Delta x = 800$ at $t/\sigma_0 = 10$. Since momenta are not formally conserved with the present scheme, we monitored the angular momentum conservation. A maximum error of 0.25% with respect to the initial angular momentum has been observed which, as visible in Fig. 10, does not substantially alter the fluid flow evolution.

Figure 12: Rotating square patch at $Re = 2000$. Temporal evolution of the kinetic energy \mathcal{E}_k obtained in APR with $L/\Delta x = 200, 400, 800$ compared to the one obtained in single-resolution configurations with $L/\Delta x = 200, L/\Delta x = 400$ and $L/\Delta x = 800$. \mathcal{E}_k^0 is the kinetic energy at $t = 0$.

6.3. Water entry of a 2D V-shaped body

Figure 13: Water entry of a 2D V-shaped body. Geometry and initial particles distribution. Left: global view of the particles size Δx . Right: zoom around the V-shaped body. Seven different particle sizes Δx are used, starting from $\Delta x_1 = 0.5mm$ close to the body up to $\Delta x_7 = 32mm$ close to the tank border, with a ratio $\Delta x_k/\Delta x_{k-1} = 2$ between two adjacent resolution levels. Each resolution level is arranged based on the refinement criteria outlined in section 5.1, ensuring that each level has a minimum thickness of $8\Delta x$.

Here, we consider the case of a V-shaped section impacting a free surface initially at rest, based on the experimental study conducted by Zhao *et al.* [94]. This scenario serves as an ideal application for APR schemes, as the area of interest is concentrated around the impact zone, allowing for a significant reduction in spatial resolution elsewhere, see *e.g.* [58, 67]. In this experimental campaign, a free falling V-shaped body with a dead-rise angle 30° , assumed as symmetric and perfectly rigid, is released above the quiescent water. The recorded velocity before entering the liquid surface is $u_0(z) = -6.15m \cdot s^{-1}$ (see also left plot of Fig. 13). The body is equipped with an accelerometer, force transducers, and five pressure sensors placed along a surface section of breadth $20cm$. The experimental setup is completed with two dummy sections (for an overall breadth of $1m$) and a drop rig for a total free falling mass of $255.5kg$. All degrees of freedom are inhibited except the vertical motion. Following the work by [58] here we choose to consider a freely falling body rather than a body with imposed vertical motion.

One of the main challenges in simulating this problem within a 2D numerical framework is the presence of significant 3D effects, resulting from the relatively short breadth b of the body compared to its length l ($l = 0.5m$ in the x-direction and $b = 1m$ in the y-direction). Note that this difficulty was already outlined in [94], in which the authors also compared their experimental results with numerical solutions obtained from a fully non-linear method based on potential theory (see also [66]).

As sketched in Fig. 13, the initial particles distribution is performed with seven levels of particle refinement (from Δx_7 down to $\Delta x_{min} = \Delta x_1$) and, as in [58, 67], the finest particles are of size

$\Delta x_1 = 0.5 \text{ mm}$. These particles are placed in a small rectangle of dimension $[528 \text{ mm}; 8 \text{ mm}]$ and the particle size is progressively increased up to $\Delta x_7 = 32 \text{ mm}$ close to the tank border. Precisely, particles of size Δx_k are placed in nested rectangles of sizes $[528 + 16 \times \sum_{l=2}^k \Delta x_l; 8 + 8 \times \sum_{l=2}^k \Delta x_l]$ (unit measure is mm), that is, keeping 8 particles between two rectangles in order to fulfil criterion (1). The resulting number of particles is 31496 at the initial instant and grows to 42839 at $t = 0.025 \text{ s}$. Compared to Approach n.2 (see also Fig. 15) a significantly smaller number of particles is required. We take advantage of this to verify whether the chosen Δx_{min} is sufficiently small to accurately capture the fluid flow solution. To this end, two additional cases with more refined particles, $\Delta x_{min} = 0.25 \text{ mm}$ and $\Delta x_{min} = 0.125 \text{ mm}$, were tested. No significant differences have been observed with respect to $\Delta x_{min} = 0.5 \text{ mm}$ (see left plot of Fig. 14), justifying the latter choice to complete the validation. Note that 13 minutes were required for the APR case with $\Delta x_{min} = 0.5 \text{ mm}$ on 8 processors, while for the single-resolution case with $\Delta x = 0.5 \text{ mm}$, 20h 54min were needed on 48 processors. Both cases ran on the same machine equipped with 48 cores Intel(R) Xeon(R) Gold 5220R CPU at 2.20GHz. As in [67] the sound speed is chosen as $c_0 = 80 \text{ m.s}^{-1}$.

Figure 14: Water entry of a 2D V-shaped body. Temporal evolution of the vertical forces exerted by the fluid on the body. Left: comparison of the present APR technique for three values of Δx_{min} with the single resolution using $\Delta x_{min} = 0.5 \text{ mm}$. Right: comparison of the present approach with other reference solutions from the literature, all with $\Delta x_{min} = 0.5 \text{ mm}$.

The results obtained with the present APR are compared to both those obtained in single resolution and reference results. The temporal evolution of the vertical forces F_Z exerted by the fluid on the body are represented in Fig. 14. Similar results are obtained between single and APR cases (see left plot). The comparison with reference results is plotted in the right plot, and a good agreement is found with the other APR approaches in SPH. The difference observed with the experimental results is due to the 3D effects as mentioned above. This good agreement is confirmed by the results in Fig. 15 where the pressure field is plotted at three different instants and compared to both the single-resolution and results from Ricci *et al.* [67]. It is worth noting that the present APR approach allows recovering a pressure field as smooth as the single-resolution case, even in transition zones where the spatial resolution changes significantly. Additionally, the pressure peak is not affected by the multi resolution, showing the advantages of Approach n.3 with respect to Approach n.2 in terms of number of particles saved.

Figure 15: Water entry of a 2D V-shaped body. Pressure profile obtained at $t = 0.00435 \text{ s}$, $t = 0.0158 \text{ s}$ and $t = 0.0202 \text{ s}$ (from top to bottom). Left column: results obtained with the present formulation. Right column: results obtained by Ricci *et al.* [67]. Contour levels are similar to those of [67] for qualitative comparison purposes. On each plot, the APR results are represented for $x < 0$; single resolution results correspond to $x \geq 0$.

The pressure profile along the body at different instant is represented in Fig. 16. For comparison purposes, the reference scales have been obtained using the recorded motion given in [94], whose numerical values are reported in Tab. 2. At all three considered time instants, the APR and single-resolution results are practically overlapping, exhibiting a smooth pressure profile. Comparisons with reference results are fair for t_2 and t_3 , whereas more pronounced differences are observed for t_1 , particularly for the pressure peak location. This is expected since t_1 corresponds to an early stage of the impact and therefore the pressure peak is more localized than instants t_2 and t_3 . Finally, bottom right plot of Fig. 16 depicts the particle size distribution against the pressure field. In this case, for better visualization, the particles are represented as circles with sizes proportional to Δx_i . This highlights again the smoothness of the pressure field in comparison to the steep gradient of the particle size.

Time (in s)	$t_1 = 0.00435$	$t_2 = 0.0158$	$t_3 = 0.0202$
Velocity references for $\frac{1}{2}\rho_0 V(t_i)^2$ (in $m.s^{-1}$)	$V(t_1) \approx -6.1008$	$V(t_2) \approx -5.3094$	$V(t_3) \approx -5.0329$
Length references (in m)	$\int_0^{t_1} V(t)dt \approx -0.02668$	$\int_0^{t_2} V(t)dt \approx -0.09255$	$z_k \approx -0.1152$ $z_D = 0.25 \times \tan(30^\circ)$

Table 2: Water entry of a 2D V-shaped body. Reference velocities and lengths used for the non-dimensionalization at times $t_1 = 0.00435$ s, $t_2 = 0.0158$ s and $t_3 = 0.0202$ s. $V(t)$ is the velocity recorded in the experiments [94]. z_k and z_D stand for the vertical coordinate of the keel and draft of the body respectively.

Figure 16: Water entry of a 2D V-shaped body. Top-left, top-right and bottom-left plots: pressure profile along the body at different instant compared to both single-resolution and reference results: $t = 0.00435$ (top left), $t = 0.0158$ (top right) and $t = 0.0202$ (bottom left), ; the legend is indicated only on the first plot for ease of readability. The reference scales used in these plots are reported in Tab. 2. Bottom right: results obtained at $t = 0.0158$ (the size of the circles are based on their actual Δx_i); the pressure field is represented on the left side of the vertical dashed-line at $x = 0$ whereas the spatial resolution is plotted on the right side.

6.4. Inviscid dam-break

The fourth test case studied is a dam-break flow impacting a vertical wall. It represents one of the most popular case in the SPH community. Several setups have been studied in the literature both experimentally and numerically. In the present work, the experiments performed by Lobovsky *et al.* [43] is retained, as represented in the left plot of Fig. 17. The reference scales are the length H , time $\sqrt{H/g}$, velocity \sqrt{Hg} and pressure $\rho_0 g H$. After the first impact on the vertical wall, the fluid flow is characterized by free-surface fragmentation and multiple breaking processes. Within the APR context, dam-break cases were studied with Approach n.1 [91] and Approach n.2 [12]. In cite [12] the finest particles were concentrated in a rectangular zone close to the pressure patch on the opposite vertical wall. In [91] a dynamic splitting close to both the free-surface and solid boundaries was used, with a maximum Δx variations of 2.8 between the finest and coarsest particles. Therefore, it represents an accurate test case to check the robustness of Approach n.3 with high Δx variations. Refinement criteria (1) \rightarrow (3) are used and the artificial speed of sound is chosen as $c_0 = 10\sqrt{Hg}$. A maximum spatial resolution of $H/\Delta x = 200$ is used and concentrated in the free-surface

region. The initial particles configuration is chosen in line with the refinement in the free-surface region, as drawn in the right plot of Fig. 17. Note that in [25] it was studied with a constant spatial resolution $H/\Delta x = 200$. Due to the high Reynolds number involved in the experiments, the hypothesis of an inviscid fluid is used here. Parallely, to avoid an overestimated numerical boundary layer due to the particles size used, free-slip boundary condition is considered. As a consequence there is no need for refining particles close to solid boundaries, that is, to activate criterion (4).

Figure 17: Inviscid dam-break. Setup of the case (left plot) and initial particle distribution (right plot).

In Fig. 18 the pressure field is represented at different instants. The free-surface shape obtained with the single-resolution $H/\Delta x = 200$ is added for comparison purposes. Before the free-surface reconnection around $t\sqrt{g/H} \approx 6.15$, *i.e.* for a potential fluid flow evolution, APR and single-resolutions results are similar, as visible in the top plots of the figure. Differences start to occur after the interface reconnection (bottom part of the figure) but, even after the cavity closure where the fluid flow evolution becomes chaotic, the principal trends observed in single-resolution are well captured in APR. Note that two phases effects are missing during the multiple cavity closure events (see *e.g.* [25]); the results are however shown until $t\sqrt{g/H} = 10$ to highlight the robustness of the present formulation, even in presence of free-surface fragmentation and reconnection. Remarkably, the pressure field is smoothed even in zones of large variations of Δx all along the simulation.

Figure 18: Inviscid dam-break. Pressure field obtained at $t\sqrt{g/H} = 3$, $t\sqrt{g/H} = 5$, $t\sqrt{g/H} = 7$ and $t\sqrt{g/H} = 10$ (from top left to bottom right). On each plot the black line corresponds to the free-surface shape obtained in single-resolution $H/\Delta x = 200$.

APR and single resolution with $H/\Delta x = 200$ are compared in terms of number of particles and CPU time at different instants in Tab. 6.4. At $t\sqrt{g/H} = 3$ both the number of particles and CPU time are more than 4 times lower in APR, for similar results (see also left plot of Fig. 19), thus representing a non negligible advantage for studying the impact on the right vertical wall event. Please note that the CPU time is obtained on a work station equipped with 48 cores Intel(R) Xeon(R) Gold 5220R CPU at 2.20GHz. Furthermore, the APR scheme is implemented in a research code which is not optimized to fully exploit the potential efficiency of the present approach. Since no coalescing procedure is used the number of particles increases during the simulation and the difference between APR and single resolution decreases. However, APR remains two times faster from $t\sqrt{g/H} = 7$ to $t\sqrt{g/H} = 10$, for comparable results. Then, although this test case was mainly studied to address the robustness feature of the proposed APR scheme, the latter has proved to be efficient in any case.

	$t\sqrt{g/H} = 3.0$	$t\sqrt{g/H} = 5.0$	$t\sqrt{g/H} = 7.0$	$t\sqrt{g/H} = 10.0$
Single resolution	80000 (25 min.)	80000 (43 min.)	80000 (60 min.)	80000 (106 min.)
APR	18039 (6 min.)	24900 (12 min.)	32463 (20 min.)	49642 (38 min.)

Table 3: Inviscid dam-break. Comparison between APR and single $H/\Delta x = 200$ resolutions in terms of number of particles and CPU time at different instants $t\sqrt{g/H} = 3, 5, 7, 10$. 8 processors on a work station machine equipped with 48 cores Intel(R) Xeon(R) Gold 5220R CPU at 2.20GHz have been used in both cases.

APR results are compared quantitatively to both single resolution and reference results in Fig. 19, where the temporal evolution of the pressure at probe P1 (located at $y = 0.01H$ on the right vertical wall) is plotted. APR and single resolution provide similar results, the main difference occurring after the interface reconnection at $t\sqrt{g/H} \approx 6.15$ where the fluid flow evolution becomes chaotic. The results are also similar to those of Hammani *et al.* [25], both in terms of time needed for impacting the right vertical wall and global trends. High-frequency noise was appearing in [25] from $t\sqrt{g/H} \approx 5.2$, which is absent with the present formulation. This beneficial effect is due to the addition of the acoustic damper term [76] in the present model. During the experimental campaign by Lobovsky *et al.* [43], a reproducibility investigation was carried out. Statistics were then performed and the average and some percentile values were provided. In Fig. 19, the grey zone corresponds to the area between the 2.5% and 97.5% percentile values. As observed the pressure pick is well captured with the present model. Nevertheless, the impact on the right vertical wall occurs slightly before the experiments and this aspect can be due to the initial gate opening (not simulated here) or to the friction between the water and the bottom wall. After the impact event, the global trend is retrieved with the present model, with a pressure overestimated from $t\sqrt{g/H} = 3$ to $t\sqrt{g/H} = 5$. Around $t\sqrt{g/H} = 5.85$, 3D effects are visible in the experiments with multiple air entrapments, which are obviously not captured with this single-phase 2D model. Then, 3D multi-phase simulations should be conducted as in [52] for instance, which is left to future work.

Figure 19: Inviscid dam-break. Temporal evolution of the pressure at probe P1 located at $y = 0.01H$ on the right vertical wall, compared to single-resolution (left plot) and reference results (right plot). For the experimental results of Lobovsky *et al.* [43] the lines correspond to the 2.5% and 97.5% percentile values of the reproducibility investigation.

6.5. Flow past an immersed cylinder at $Fr = 1$ and $Re = 180$

Figure 20: Flow past an immersed cylinder at $Fr = 1$ and $Re = 180$. Sketch of the problem geometry.

In the present section, a flow past an immersed cylinder in an open channel is investigated. This problem was firstly simulated with SPH in [9] and corresponds to the “Sequence 2” of that article. Precisely, the Froude and Reynolds numbers are respectively set to $Fr = U_0/\sqrt{gd} = 1$ and $Re = \rho_0 U_0 d/\mu = 180$ with U_0 the inflow velocity, g the gravity magnitude and d the diameter of the cylinder. The ratio between the cylinder immersion and cylinder diameter is $h/d = 1.5$, and the fluid depth is $\frac{H+h}{d} = 6$ as represented in Fig. 20. The reference scales are the length d , the velocity U_0 , the time d/U_0 , the vorticity U_0/d , the pressure $\frac{1}{2}\rho_0 U_0^2$ and the force $\frac{1}{2}\rho_0 U_0^2 d$. The drag coefficient is defined as $C_D(t) = \frac{F_x(t)}{\frac{1}{2}\rho_0 d U_0^2}$, F_x being the force exerted by the fluid onto the cylinder in the horizontal direction. This test case was then studied in [11], in order to validate a coupling between the SPH and FV methods. The SPH method was used in a small zone above the cylinder to better capture the free-surface deformation in this zone, whereas the FV method was employed elsewhere. These results are adopted here as reference solution.

Figure 21: Flow past an immersed cylinder at $Fr = 1$ and $Re = 180$. Top plots: spatial resolution Δx_i obtained with criterion (5) (left) and without (right). Bottom plots: zoom around the cylinder; the orange dashed-line highlights the effect of criterion (5) onto the extension of the finest resolution region, upstream of the stagnation point on the cylinder wall.

Figure 22: Flow past an immersed cylinder at $Fr = 1$ and $Re = 180$. Temporal evolution of the drag coefficient C_D . Comparison between results obtained with APR with criterion (5), APR without criterion (5) and with single resolution.

The minimum spatial resolution is fixed to $\Delta x_{min} = d/50$ with four refinement levels enabled for a maximum spatial resolution of $\Delta x = d/6.25$. The inflow and outflow limits are positioned vertically at $x_{in}/d = -11$ and $x_{out}/d = 22$ respectively. The spatial resolution for the inflow is managed to be in line with the criterion (3) (as visible in Fig. 21), that is using $\Delta x = d/50$ for $y/d \geq 1.84$, $\Delta x = d/25$ for $y/d \in [1.52; 1.84[$, $\Delta x = d/12.5$ for $y/d \in [0.88; 1.52[$ and $\Delta x = d/6.25$ for $y/d < 0.88$.

For the considered flow regime, a breaking wave is generated downstream the cylinder. At each breaking cycle the plunging jet produces a vortical structure. The latter couples with the vortices in the underlying von Kármán wake generated by the cylinder (see Figs. 23 and 24). In order to capture these phenomena, a fine resolution is needed at the free surface as well as in the boundary layer around the cylinder. Therefore, from a numerical point of view, criteria (1) \rightarrow (4) are activated, that is, in the free-surface region with

criterion (3) and close to the cylinder surface (criterion (4), disabled at the bottom part of the tank). Using these criteria the drag coefficient C_D obtained with APR exhibits a difference of about 10% from the one obtained in single-resolution at $\Delta x = d/50$ as shown in Fig. 22. Note that a moving average filter with time window equal to $\Delta t = 0.5d/U_0$ has been applied to the force signals. Consequently, another refinement criterion is added based on the dynamic pressure P_{dyn} . To smooth out the dynamic pressure field, a mollification is employed, and this criterion (5) precisely reads:

$$\frac{\tilde{P}_{dyn}^i}{0.5\rho_0 U_0^2} > 0.45, \quad \text{where} \quad \tilde{P}_{dyn}^i = \frac{1}{\Gamma_i} \sum_j [P_j - \rho_0 \mathbf{g} \cdot (\mathbf{x}_j - \mathbf{x}_0)] W_{ij} V_j$$

where \mathbf{x}_0 is the reference position of the free surface. Fig. 21 reports the comparison of the particle size distribution with and without the inclusion of criterion (5). The adoption of the latter implies only a slight enlargement of the region characterized by the finest resolution. Precisely, this occurs upstream the stagnation point on the cylinder wall (highlighted with orange dashed line in the figure). Thanks to this small extension of the high resolution region, results similar to the single-resolution case are recovered in terms of drag coefficient as shown in Fig. 22.

Figure 23: Flow past an immersed cylinder at $Fr = 1$ and $Re = 180$. Dynamic pressure (left) and vorticity (right) fields at $tU_0/d = 62.5$. In both cases a zoom around the cylinder is provided in the bottom plots.

In Fig. 23 the dynamic pressure (left plots) and vorticity fields (right plots) are represented at $tU_0/d = 62.5$. The obtained fields are smooth, even in zones of large Δx variations (see also Fig. 21). The vorticity field is compared to both single-resolution and reference results by Chiron *et al.* [11] in Fig. 24. A very good agreement is observed. Notably, the vortex patterns are remarkably similar both in terms of vortex localization and magnitude. Small differences are noted especially close to the free-surface, and they are due to the chaotic behavior induced by the breaking of the free-surface. It is worth remarking that the present APR scheme produces the same results as the single-resolution case with a CPU time around 4 times lower, as shown in Tab. 4. Note that the employment of APR is not useful exclusively for CPU costs, but also for data storage and post-processing time.

Figure 24: Flow past an immersed cylinder at $Fr = 1$ and $Re = 180$. Vorticity field obtained in APR (centre) compared to single-resolution results (top) and results by Chiron *et al.* [11] (bottom). For the results in [11], the rectangle in dashed line represents the SPH zone whereas FV was used elsewhere.

	$tU_0/d = 10$	$tU_0/d = 20$	$tU_0/d = 40$	$tU_0/d = 80$
Single resolution	496597 (3h 15 min)	498087 (6h 31 min)	498155 (13h 29 min)	498695 (27h 35 min)
APR	67550 (20 min)	95510 (50 min)	126715 (2h 40 min)	110208 (6 h 40 min)

Table 4: Flow past an immersed cylinder at $Fr = 1$ and $Re = 180$. Number of particles and CPU time required at different instants, compared to single-resolution $\Delta x = d/50$. 42 processors on a work station machine equipped with 48 cores Intel(R) Xeon(R) Gold 5220R CPU at 2.20GHz have been used in both cases.

Finally, the temporal evolution of the drag coefficient is compared to reference results in Fig. 25. The transient part is different but, once the quasi-periodic regime is reached (*i.e.* around $tU_0/d = 55$), similar results are observed both in terms of period and amplitude. Note that for comparison purposes and since the vortex shedding did not start at the same instant for all the results, a time-shift has been applied to the reference results.

Figure 25: Flow past an immersed cylinder at $Fr = 1$ and $Re = 180$. Temporal evolution of the drag coefficient C_D compared to the reference results by Chiron *et al.* [11] and Bouscasse *et al.* [9]. A zoom is provided on the right plot of the figure.

7. Conclusion

In the present work, an in-depth analysis of the existing works about APR in SPH has shown that, in fact, most of the techniques derived in the literature can be categorized into three main approaches. These approaches mainly depend on the selected SPH operators. In particular, the adoption of accurate SPH operators (Approach n.3) enable for large variations of the particle sizes without the need for buffer regions nor variable smoothing length treatments. However, this approach has been restricted to internal flows due to inherent difficulties to treat the free-surface with these type of operators. Recently in [50], the RHOD-SPH scheme has been derived, where accurate but non-conservative operators are employed in the bulk of fluid and conservative ones in the free-surface region. However, this scheme was restricted to single-resolution cases.

Then, in the present work, the RHOD-SPH scheme has been generalized for APR purposes, resulting in an extension of Approach n.3 to free-surface flows. To this end, Riemann-based diffusive terms in the SPH context have been generalized to particle of different sizes. An extension of the PST has also been proposed. A splitting procedure has been employed with refinement close to the free-surface or to solid boundaries. Thus making the present APR scheme flexible and efficient. Particularly, the choices made here allow for preserving a “gather”-type of implementation which are particularly effective with GPU accelerators. The validation has been performed on five different cases. Similar results have been obtained in APR and single resolution even for challenging cases with a significant gain in terms of computational cost, reduction of post-processing time consumption and data savings, especially compared to APR techniques using buffer regions. The results have also been compared to reference results, showing a good agreement. The resulting formulation is easy to implement and turned out to be robust, at least for 2D test cases. Additionally, the use of generic refinement criteria based on the flow fields (*e.g.* pressure, velocity gradients, etc) can be straightforwardly included in the present framework. The development of a suitable particle coalescing procedure and extension to the 3D framework are left to future work.

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